

Redness Rating of Horizons of Soil Profiles Located on Different Parent Materials in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Redness rating (RR) was evaluated for horizons of soil profiles located on sedimentary deposits and basement complex parent materials found in Niger state, Nigeria in the research. Findings showed that soils on the sedimentary deposits and basement complex have colours that could be described at 7.5 contrast of Yellow-Red (YR) hue with value of between 3 and 5, and chroma of between 3 and 8 for the soils formed on the sedimentary deposits but value of between 3 and 7, and chroma of between 1 and 8 for the soils formed on the basement complex. The colours of the horizons were between strong brown and dusky red for the soils formed on the sedimentary deposits while the soils formed on the basement complex exhibited between Grey and Strong brown colours within their profiles. The RR value of the soils was found to be between 2.00 and 12.00 for the sedimentary deposits, and between 0.50 and 3.33 for the basement complex. No significant relationship was established between RR and organic matter content as well as with clay content. It expedient that the RR values of soils at various locations be evaluated and related to other soil properties because this can be of predictive value, for instance, in determining excessive, insufficient, sufficient and toxic levels of some micro-nutrients such as iron and manganese which usually affect crop production.

Keywords: Chroma, Horizons, Hue, Parent Materials, Redness Rating

Introduction

Interpretation of soils lays strong emphasis on their colours (Hammonds, 2013). Nutrient content of a soil is easily reflected in its color and mineral composition. Hence, interaction of light and different constituents of a soil is shown in its look (Torrent & Barron, 1993). Characteristics of the mineral and organic components of influence to a very great extent other properties of soil, color inclusive that determine the appearance of soil. These soil properties could be inferred from soil colour and eventually, utilized for soil classification. The condition and content of materials in soils, such as air, water, organic matter and oxides could be revealed by soil colour. For instance, soils with high organic matter content are dark, wet conditions with shortage of oxygen are grey coloured, whereas soils with surplus oxygen are brown.

The influence of organic matter is evident in soil appearing darker - brown to black in colour (humus rich soil being black). Sodium causes the organic matter (humus) to disperse more readily and spread over the soil particles, making the soil look darker (black) (Victorian Resources Online, 2017). The redox behavior of soils emanate from weathering processes which subsequently determines the expression of colours in soil profiles. Generally, the situations which the soil is exposed to are revealed in the colour eventually exhibited. This colour could be gray, black, white, reds, browns, yellows and under the right conditions, green (Nyle & Weil, 2006). Predictive efficacies of soil colours can be privy in so many circumstances such as oxidized ferric iron oxides are revealed in yellow or red colours; soils with high content of organic matter have dark brown or black color; meanwhile, wet soils appear darker than dry soil (Nyle & Weil, 2006). Further implication of soil colour are possibilities of inferring oxygen level or state with soils that are well-drained (high O₂ content) being red and brown because of increased oxidation and wet soils (low O₂) are usually grey or greenish because of enhanced reduction, particularly of iron; black colour may also reveal high content of manganese oxide mineral; glauconite rich soil are green; and the calcite would make soil whitish (Nyle & Weil, 2006).

Besides parent materials and topographies, soil management strategies result to temporal and spatial variation in soil properties. As emphasized by McBratney and Pringle (1999) that agricultural management practices can be improved through proper harnessing of soil properties distribution at the field scale in order to curtail environmental degradation. Colour is one of the most apparent and most significant characteristics of soil, consistently used as a definitive criterion in the identification, classification and separation of soil (Bhavanarayana, 2001; Sanchez-Maranon *et al.*, 2004). Soil colour

is measured using Munsell Soil Color charts (Munsell Colour Company, 1975). The Munsell system provides a standardized reference for determining soil hue, intensity and darkness. Soil patterns, or mottling, are examined to determine water content and the level of water that was in soil from previous seasons.

Statement of Problem

Although soil colour is always taken cognizance of in soil studies, particularly, pedological studies (that is, in survey and classification studies), less importance is accorded to its usefulness. This is probably due to the fact that colour is assumed to be of a qualitative value which usually all objects possess. It may almost be unperceivable that soil colours can be quantified, and relating it to other properties such as organic matter and texture (clay). Also, the quantitative approaches for soil colours are very cumbersome and require expensive gadgets that are hardly affordable to many agencies, organizations and individuals concerned with soil studies, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Devising simpler approaches of quantifying soil colour requires taciturn utilization of available means of qualifying colour, which is provided in the Munsell system.

Quantifying colour of soils formed on different parent materials and relating such to other properties can reveal some pertinent information and serve predictive purposes of the functions that soils may perform. Utilizing a simple approach that gives clue and predictive value to soil colour is eminent and timely not only for its express research value but for practical applications in agriculture and engineering. Hence, the research determined soil colour for profiles located on different parent materials, evaluate the redness rating of such horizons and determine the relationships between organic matter content, texture (clay) and the redness rating of the soils.

Materials and Methods

Area of Study

The research was carried out in Niger state. The state lies between latitudes 8.0° and 11°30' N, and Longitudes 03°30' and 07°40' E. The state experiences two distinct seasons, the dry and wet seasons. The annual rainfall varies from about 1,600 mm in the south to 1,200 mm in the north. The duration of the rainy season ranges between 150 and 210 days or more in the north and the south respectively (Ayinde *et al.*, 2013).

The sedimentary and basement complex rocks are found over the state landscape. The sedimentary rocks to the south are characterized of sandstones and alluvial deposits, particularly along the Niger valley and in most parts of Borgu, Bida, Agaie, Lapai, Mokwa, Lavun, Gbako and Wushishi Local Government Areas. This sub-area also contains the extensive flood plains of the River Niger and this has made the state to be one of the largest and most fertile agricultural lands in the country. It also provides the best area for rice growing in Nigeria. Perhaps this may account for the location of the National Cereals Research Institute at Badeggi in the state.

Figure 1 Geological Map of Niger State (Source: Nigerian Data Mall, 2016)

Research Procedure

Soil profiles of 100 cm depth were dug at six locations in six different local government areas of the state. At each site, the geographical positioning system (GPS) was used to determine the longitude, latitude and altitude. Then, the horizons of soil profile at each location were identified and described as seen in the field. Also, the physiographic features of the land and land use in the area were described.

Then, soil samples were collected from each horizon of the profiles, prepared and analyzed for pertinent soil properties such as organic matter, iron content and texture. Also, redness rating of each horizon was calculated.

Data Collection

Data on redness rating, organic matter content and texture of horizons as well as GPS location of the sampling points were collected. Soil colour was measured using the Munsell Soil Colour Chart (Munsell Colour Company, 1975) at YR hue and the redness rating (RR) was determined using the methods stated in Torrent *et al.* (1983) and defined as:

$$RR = (10-H) \times \frac{C}{V};$$

Where H is the number preceding YR in the Munsell hue, C is the chroma and V is the value.

Soil organic matter was determined with the wet oxidation method (Walkley and Black, 1934) and texture of soils was determined using the hydrometer technique (Day, 1965) whereas longitudes, latitudes and altitudes were determined using the GPS.

Research Design and Data Analysis

The research was designed as a split-split-plot arrangement fitted into randomized complete block design (RCBD) as illustrated in figure 2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and correlation analysis were employed to analyze data collected. Means in all cases were separated using the Standard Error of Means (SEM).

	A			B		
	I	II	III	I	II	III
1						
2						
3						
4						

Figure 2 Schematization of Research Design

A and B represent the geological formations

I, II, III represent the local government areas (locations of mini-profiles)

1, 2, 3, 4 represent the horizons of each profile

Results and Discussion

Description of the Location of the Soil Profiles

Three soil profiles were located on the sedimentary deposits of Niger state at Bida, Mokwa and Ibbi. Those locations on the sedimentary deposits lie between latitudes 9.04°N and 9.66°N , and longitudes 4.91°E and 6.00°E at altitudes between 88 m and 187 m above sea level. The land features around the soil profiles on the sedimentary deposits revealed that they are all flat upland used for crop production; however, tree species predominant in the area include gmelina, teak, shea butter, cashew, locust bean and mango. The other three soil profiles were located on the basement complex at Kuta, Kagara and Rijau which are positioned between latitudes 9.86°N and 11.10°N , and longitudes 5.27°E and 6.71°E at altitudes of between 253.5 m and 349.0 m above sea level. The gradient of the land ranged from a gentle slope to a flat surface with locust bean and mango as predominant tree species.

The geographical coordinates are in tandem with the general description for the land area of Niger state by Niger State Bureau of Statistics (2012). These physiographic features are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Description of Location of Soil Profiles around Niger State, Nigeria

Location	Coordinates	Altitude	Topography/Land Use
PARENT MATERIAL: SEDIMENTARY DEPOSITS			
BidaPoly	9.04°N , 6.0°E	187.0m	Flat upland with guinea corn farmland.
Mokwa	9.30°N , 5.06°E	88.0m	Flat upland with Gmelina and Teak as predominant tree species and grasses.
Ibbi	9.66°N , 4.91°E	111.0m	Flat land with cashew, Gmelina and Shea butter. Not used for >5yrs.

PARENT MATERIAL: BASEMENT COMPLEX

Kuta as the	9.86 ⁰ N, 6.71 ⁰ E	292.5m	Gentle slope with locust predominant plant species	bean and mango
Kagara as the	10.18 ⁰ N, 6.27 ⁰ E	253.5m	Gentle slope with locust predominant plant species.	bean and mango
Rijau	11.1 ⁰ N, 5.27 ⁰ E	349.0m	Flat upland with planted mango.	

Colour and Redness Rating of Soil at Different Locations in Niger State

Soil colour for the horizons of the soils on the sedimentary deposits varies between brown and red on the Munshell colour system. The hue of the colour was mainly at 7.5 contrast in the yellow-red (YR) wavelength with value between 3 and 5 and chroma of between 3 and 8. In the Munshell colour system, hue identifies the basic spectral color or wavelength (Red, Yellow, Blue, or in-between, such as Yellow-Red, amongst others); value indicates the degree of lightness or darkness or reflectance of an object viewed in daylight; and chroma represents the color intensity, saturation or relative strength of color—that is, the degree of departure from a gray of the same value (Hammonds, 2013).

For the horizons of the soils formed on the basement complex, the soil colour varies between gray, brown yellow to red on the Munshell colour system. The hue was also mainly at contrast of 7.5 in the YR wavelength with value between 3 and 7 and chroma of between 1 and 8. Tables 2 and 3 show the results for colours of horizons for the soils formed on the sedimentary deposits and basement complex respectively. The RR values were between 2.00 and 12.00 for the sedimentary deposits’ soils; between 0.50 and 3.33 for the basement complex soils. However, there was no significant difference between the RR values of the soils and their horizons. Results of RR values of the soils are contained in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 Colour Description of Horizons and RR of Soil Profiles on Sedimentary Deposits

Location	Horizon Labels	Colour	RR (Redness Rating)
BidaPoly	A _p	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁴ / ₆ moist)	3.75

	A _h	Brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₄ moist)	2.00
	E	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₈ moist)	4.00
	B _t	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₈ moist)	4.00
Mokwa	A _p	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁴ / ₆ moist)	3.75
	A _h	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₈ moist)	4.00
	E	Red (2.5 YR ⁵ / ₈ moist)	12.00
	B _t	Red (2.5 YR ⁴ / ₆ moist)	11.25
Ibbi	A _p	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁴ / ₆ moist)	3.75
	A _h	Brown (7.5 YR ⁴ / ₄ moist)	2.50
	E	Dusky red (7.5 YR ³ / ₃ moist)	2.50
	B _t	Red (7.5 YR ⁴ / ₈ moist)	5.00

Table 3 Colour Description of Horizons and RR of Soil Profiles on Basement Complex

Location	Horizon Labels	Colour Description	RR
4. Kuta	A _p	Dark reddish gray (2.5YR ⁴ / ₁ moist)	1.88
	A _h	Reddish gray (2.5 YR ⁵ / ₁ moist)	1.50
	E	Brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₃ moist)	1.50
	B _t	Pale red (2.5 YR ⁶ / ₂ moist)	2.50
5. Kagara	A _p	Dark brown (7.5 YR ³ / ₂ moist)	1.67
	A _h	Dark brown (7.5 YR ³ / ₃ moist)	2.50
	EC	Grey (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₁ moist)	0.50
	C	Reddish yellow (7.5 YR ⁶ / ₆ moist)	2.50
6. Rijau	A _p	Reddish yellow (7.5 YR ⁷ / ₈ moist)	2.86
	A _h	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁵ / ₆ moist)	3.00
	E	Reddish yellow (7.5 YR ⁷ / ₆ moist)	2.14

B _t	Strong brown (7.5 YR ⁶ / ₈ moist)	3.33
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Table 4 Clay and Organic Matter Contents of Horizons of Soils on Different Parent Material

Parent Material		Parent Material				
Sedimentary Deposits	Horizon	Clay	OM	Basemen Complex	Clay	OM
BidaPoly	A _p	12.54	0.33	Kuta	24.66	0.43
	A _h	13.54	0.28		24.66	0.36
	E	14.54	0.26		24.66	0.31
	B _t	15.04	0.22		25.66	0.10
Mokwa	A _p	6.54	0.86	Kagara	6.54	0.96
	A _h	10.54	0.59		11.54	0.79
	E	14.54	0.55		13.54	0.62
	B _t	14.54	0.50		12.31	0.55
Ibbi	A _p	7.56	0.31	Rijau	24.84	0.07
	A _h	8.56	0.36		20.84	0.12
	E	10.56	0.41		18.84	0.17
	B _t	15.56	0.46		15.84	0.22

Relationships between RR, Clay and Organic Matter Content

The clay and organic matter contents of the soils are contained in Table 4. There was no significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) between the contents of clay and organic matter of the soils with respect to both locations of the profiles and parent materials from which the soils were formed. The coefficients of correlation (r) for the parameters show that clay and organic matter content have slight effect on soil colour, particularly, in determining how red or otherwise a soil would look. It is known that redness or other colours of soils are usually due to oxidation of metallic oxides in soils such as iron and manganese oxides (Torrent and Barron, 1993). The correlation coefficients for the relationships of RR and CC, RR and OM, and, CC and OM are shown in Table 5 with only CC and OM showing significant relationship ($P \leq 0.05$) with $r = -0.624$.

Table 5 Correlation Coefficients Matrix for Redness Rating (RR), Clay Content (CC) and Organic Matter Content (OM)

	RR	CC	OM
Redness Rating	1		
Clay Content	-0.144	1	
Organic Matter Content	0.091	-0.624*	1

Conclusion

Colours of soils are usually a property of pedological importance as well as artistic significance. The redness rating provides a clue for defining soil colour at Yellow-Red hue, of which most soils in the tropics can be described with. The research has shown that colour of the soils from the profiles can be conveniently described as such and thereby providing predictive tool for prominent processes such as braunification, rubification, oxidation or reduction amongst others that could be responsible for soil development in the locations. Agriculturally, the RR of soils can be applied to infer the fertility and suitability of a soil for crop production.

Recommendations

The following recommendations can be made based on the findings of the research:

- i. Determination of RR value of a soil is necessary as it can be used to predict if some micro-nutrients such as iron and manganese are at toxic levels.
- ii. Processes of soil formation can be inferred from the RR value
- iii. However, there should be correlation established for the RR value and soil properties to be predicted from it.
- iv. Artists can use the RR value in the search of soil of a particular colour which they put to use in their artistic practices such as sculpture production, ceramics manufacture, amongst others.

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